

Supporting Elite Gaelic Games Student-Athletes in Higher Education

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Further Reading:

Whelan, C., Ryan, L., Gomez, J., & Daly, E. (2026) Perceived barriers to balancing sport and study among elite Gaelic games student-athletes. *Managing Sport and Leisure*, 1–22. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/23750472.2026.2651423>

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Rationale, Aims and Objectives

Elite Gaelic games student-athletes (EGSAs) inter-county players simultaneously enrolled in full-time higher education face unique dual-career pressures. Unlike professional pathway athletes, EGSAs receive no financial remuneration yet compete at professional performance standards, while managing full academic workloads without a centralised institutional support system. This research examined the most significant perceived barriers to balancing sport and study among EGSAs, identified the key predictors of dual-career strain, and generated evidence to inform policy and practice in both sport and higher education.

Research Findings

A cross-sectional survey of 320 elite Gaelic games student-athletes identified three major barriers to balancing sport and study: institutional, time and geographical constraints. Institutional rigidity, including inflexible academic scheduling, limited lecturer awareness and poor coordination between sport and education systems, was the strongest predictor of strain. Higher training loads increased time pressure, although athletes completing shorter, more structured sessions reported lower strain. Travel between university, home and training venues affected 45% of participants, adding further burden to already demanding schedules. Coping capacity emerged as the strongest protective factor, with athletes better able to manage competing demands reporting substantially lower levels of strain across all barrier domains.

Policy Implications

These barriers are structural, not individual - they are produced by systems not designed for the dual-career athlete. Addressing them requires coordinated action between higher education institutions, national governing bodies, and government. These findings also suggest that coping capacity is the single most powerful modifiable resource available to athletes navigating these conditions. Developing coping and self-regulation skills through embedded psychoeducational programmes should therefore be a priority alongside structural reform, not as a substitute for it, but as a parallel investment in athletes' ability to manage demands that no institutional redesign will fully eliminate.

Industry Recommendations

Higher education institutions and national governing bodies should implement coordinated dual-career support frameworks for elite Gaelic games student-athletes, including flexible academic scheduling, improved lecturer awareness, athlete welfare supports, and training and competition structures that avoid overlap with examinations and college competitions. The proposed 2027 GAA/LGFA/Camogie merger should embed dual-career athlete welfare as a core governance priority, with standardised supports implemented consistently across all codes.

